

ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING PROFESSION AMONG PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS IN SHIVAMOGGA CITY

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Abstract:

Education is the back bone of our country and student's progress also depends on education. But no education system can be better than the quality of its teacher and no skill can be developed without help of a teacher. Present study was conducted in Shivamogga city; Here 200 Pre-service teachers (50 from each college) from Four B.Ed. colleges were randomly selected for data collection. There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude scores towards teaching profession in the economic area of male and female Pre-service teachers. There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude scores towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitudes of teachers towards teaching profession. The mean teacher attitudes scores of female teachers in total area was found to be greater than ($X=171.06$) their counterpart that is male Pre-service teachers ($X=164.20$) respectively. There is no significant difference in mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession scores in the academic and co-curricular areas and total scores of rural and urban pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.

Key words: Attitude, Pre-Service Teachers, Teaching Profession & Shivamogga

Introduction:

Education is the background of any progressing nation and the teachers are the pivot in any system of education as she has a key role to perform in the whole progress. Teachers form an important role in the development of society. This is often reflected in the kinds of tribute that are paid to the teachers such as "Teachers are nation builders". Teaching is one of the noble professions. It is obvious that all teachers cannot claim to be worthy of these statements. It is only the effective teachers who can in some measure be worthy of thought that is placed in her by society. Surely an efficient teacher can and does bring about desirable changes in the students and deserves to be called a nation builder. A requisite sound knowledge of the subject matter and the personality traits as acquired by the teachers would assure for them to be effective and they would develop a positive attitude towards teacher profession (Anshu Vasishtha Patel and Rakesh, 2012-13).

Teaching is incredibly rewarding when individuals have worked diligently with success in reaching students and allowing them to reach their potential growth. Thus teaching is an activity that includes the student and teacher interaction in the class that is necessary to make him/her aware about the aspects of teaching, moreover to precede the students towards the perfection in teaching field. During courses of teaching pupil teachers are provided opportunities of "Teaching Practice (Sarita, 2014).

The teacher's roles and responsibilities have found extension outside the classroom. The implementation of educational policies, transaction of curricula and spreading awareness are the main areas which keep teacher in the forefront. Changing times have added new dimension to this profession, which requires specified competencies and right attitude. Behaviour, attitude and interest of teacher help in shaping the personality of the student. Attitude is a tendency to react in a particular

manner towards the stimuli (Anastasi,1957; Anupama Bhargava and Pathy, 2014).Therefore, to reach the goal the role of the teacher is very significant and vital in imparting good education.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the study were to examine whether the gender and locality (rural/urban) has significant difference on the attitudes of Pre-service teachers towards teaching profession. The study is undertaken by the investigator with the following objectives in view.

- ✓ To Study the significant difference in attitude towards teaching profession among Pre-service teachers with respect to their Genders.
- ✓ To Study the significant difference in attitude towards teaching profession among Pre-service teachers with respect to their locality.

Need and Importance of the Study:

The teacher, by virtue of his position and role, is one of the most important agent of the preservation and enrichment of culture in to-day's society. Having to deal with human material during the most impressionable period of life, the teacher is bound to make massive impact on the personality character, intellectual growth, attitudes, and values of the future citizens. In view of their role it is incumbent to meet the challenges of their task and our Indian society is no exertion to it.

Unfortunately in India to-day, the socio- economic status and the professional status of teachers at the primary level are far too below the standards despite many efforts made to improve to it. The status of education as an academic study must be raised. This is one of the factors for school teaching to emerge as an established profession, like law medicine, engineering etc., unless teaching attains the status of profession and teachers as professionals; it is idle to harbor the high expectations that we as a nation have from our teachers and to have right attitudes towards their profession.

In view of the above observation, there is dire need to understand the attitude of Pre-service teachers towards teaching profession. The abilities, attitudes, personality traits, family and educational background of Pre-service teachers are said to be related to the effectiveness of teaching profession of the Pre-service teachers.

Importance of the Study:

The significance of the problem depends on to a great extent upon how it is related to the present day conditions of rapid social change. The quality of education in a country legally depends on the quality of the teacher. It is said that educational level can't rise if the quality of teachers are not raised. A good teacher is always above to the nation. Priceless and valuable gain to be adorned and enviable personality to be adverse. In fact the country's progress is possible only when its teachers are higher in status and have depth of knowledge. A good teacher means good and lasting education.

Dr. Zakir Hussein has emphasized the quality of a teacher as follows. "Quality of a teacher is more important than all other factors put together, viz., syllabus, text books, equipments and buildings. If we can't secure a teaching professional that is keen and intelligent and has a high sense of duty and integrity and if we can't see them reasonably satisfied and contested in their work no educational scheme can have the slighter change of success, that is why the most important scheme in the reconstructions of education, in the country relates to the improvements of the qualification, the status and prospects of the teachers that are the present surprisingly low".

Studies conducted on social, economic and professional status of primary school teachers show their pathetic state of living conditions, majority of teachers feel "taking

up a teaching profession is to invite miseries and difficulties in life. So it has a never invited or attached to the young, energetic and well telemeter men and women”.

Since primary education is the foundation stone on which the whole super structure has to be built, one must think of improving the quality of primary education. This can be made possible only when their status is improved to motivate the teachers to have possible out look towards the profession.

Viewing the above factors it is considered that teacher is the only important and vital element for educational reconstruction. Unless this factors receiving adequate considerations, reforms in other fields may not yield good results.

Therefore in the present study an attempt was made to study the Pre-service teachers attitude towards teaching profession with reference to their, gender and locality on a selected population of B.Ed colleges of Shivamogga city.

Methodology of the Study:

Methodology comprises details regarding the design of the study, operational definitions of some of the terms used in this research, discussion of the variables, hypothesis, tools used for the collection of data, sampling procedure and the procedures adopted for the analysis of data are discussed in this chapter. The purpose of the present investigation is to study the attitudes of the Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level towards teaching profession.

The present study is descriptive type in which investigator tries to find out the Pre-service teachers attitude towards teacher profession. The selected B.Ed Colleges were one aided and three unaided private educational institutions. Out of the total populations of Pre-service teachers only 200 of them were selected for the present study.

The investigator adopted normative survey type for collecting the data from Pre-service teachers of various institutions. An attitude scale towards teaching profession which contained a set of statements pertaining to teaching profession was given to the Pre-service teachers. After collecting the data the analysis and interpretation was carried on.

For the purpose of present study the definition given by Kulsum for attitudes of teacher towards teaching profession has been followed as “Attitudes of secondary school teachers towards their profession”, has been operational with reference to their attitudes towards:

- ✓ Academic aspects of teaching profession.
- ✓ Administrative aspects of teaching profession.
- ✓ Social and physiological aspects of teaching profession.
- ✓ Co-curricular aspect of teaching profession.
- ✓ Economic aspect of teaching profession.

The above aspects will be discussed in detail in tools of the study.

Types of Institutional Management:

Aided Institutions:

Aided institutions are those which are managed by secretary of the institution partially involving the government, headed by a superintendent appointed by the secretary of the institution. Then follows all the procedures laid down by the state government. The number of students taken in this study consists of those from private and aided institutions.

Unaided Institutions:

These institutions are purely managed by the management and administered by superintendent appointed and supervised by management and secretary of the

institution. They follow the state syllabus and the procedure lay down by the private management. The number of Pre-service teachers taken in the study consists of those from unaided institutions.

Sampling Procedure:

The sample of the present study constitutes the pupil of the B.Ed colleges of Shivamogga City. The total number of Pre-service teachers in the Aided and unaided institutions was identified as the population for the study.

200 Pre-service teachers from aided and unaided B.Ed colleges were chosen as samples. These 200 Pre-service teachers were administered with the following tool for obtaining data for the present study,

‘An attitude scale towards teaching profession developed and standardized by Kulsum (2001)’

The sample frame given below provides the details of sample distribution over school management. Table showing distribution of sample over type of management

Type of Institution Management	Total No. of Institution	No. of Pre-Service Teachers	Total
Aided	1	50	50
Unaided	3	150	150
Total	4	200	200

Statistical Tools of the Study:

The research tools used for the study are discussed in detail in the following: To measure the teacher attitude of B.Ed colleges' Pre-service teachers, Attitude scale towards teaching profession standardized by Kulsum (2001) was used.

Scoring of Statement:

For the purpose of scoring the positive and negative statements that were traced at the numerical weights as below were assigned-Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

S.No	Type of Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	Positive	8	6	4	2
2	Negative	2	4	6	8

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

In this study, methodology adopted was discussed in detail. The data collected has been analyzed and interpreted. This has been done as per the arrangements of variables in the questionnaires. While doing the analysis, the details are presented in each table and null hypothesis have been formulated for this purpose. Each one of the hypothesis are examined by the investigator using statistical tools.

To test the significance of the difference between the levels of attitudes towards teaching profession at B.Ed level as per differences in the variables like gender and locality selected for the study, the mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ values are found out. The interpretations are as follows:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude score towards teaching profession in the area of academic, administrative, Co-curricular, socio-psychological and economic aspect of attitudes of the male and female Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude score towards teaching profession in the total attitudes of male and female Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.

Differences in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession (area wise and total) of male and female Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level, as per differences in the independent variable selected for the study.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession scores in the areas of academic, administrative, co-curricular, socio-psychological as well as economic aspects and total scores of male and female Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.

Table 1: Size, Mean, Standard Deviation and obtained 't' value with the level of significance at 0.05 and 0.01 level of mean teacher attitude scores in the 5 areas and total scores of Male and Female Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.

Area under attitude towards teaching profession	Male			Female			't' value	Significance Level
	N	X	SD	N	X	SD		
Academic	95	31.20	3.4	105	33.34	3.4	2.34	*
Administrative	95	18.50	2.6	105	19.50	2.2	3.52	**
Co-curricular	95	15.80	2.1	105	16.9	3.1	3.78	**
Socio-psychological	95	81.10	5.9	105	83.21	6.5	2.45	*
Economic	95	2.48	2.4	105	19.09	2.6	1.89	NS
Total	95	164.2	10.12	105	171.06	12.4	3.98	**

From the Table 1 it can be observed that the obtained 't' value in the case of one area that is economic aspect of B.Ed Pre-service teachers towards teaching profession was not significant even at 0.05 level, as the obtained 't' value of 1.89 is not significant even at 0.05 level of significant as it is less than the table value of t (99, 0.05= 1.98). Thus the null hypothesis, namely, there is no significant differences in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the economic area of male and female pupil teacher at B.Ed level is accepted.

Table 2: Size, Mean, Standard Deviation and obtained 't' value with the level of significance at 0.05 and 0.01 level of mean teacher attitude scores in the 5 areas and total scores of Married and Unmarried Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level

Area under attitude towards teaching profession	Rural			Urban			't' value	Level of Significance
	N	X	SD	N	X	SD		
Academic	90	32.67	3.2	110	32.85	3.4	0.67	NS
Administrative	90	18.94	2.3	110	18.62	2.1	4.45	**
Co-curricular	90	16.05	3.1	110	15.22	2.2	0.86	NS
Socio-psychological	90	80.45	4.8	110	82.64	6.8	4.88	**
Economic	90	18.50	2.4	110	18.26	2.45	3.08	**
Total	90	164.12	9.4	110	170.25	11.48	4.82	**

T (198, 0.05) =1.98

T (198, 0.01) =2.63

As per Table 2. There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the academic, co-curricular areas of rural and urban pre service teachers at B.Ed level.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession scores in the 2 areas (namely Academic and co-curricular) and total scores of rural and urban Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level. In Table 2, it can be observed that the obtained 't' value in the case of one area that is economic aspect of B.Ed Pre-service teachers towards teaching profession was significant at 0.05 level, as the obtained 't' value are significant at 0.05 level (t 99, 0.05= 1.98). Thus the null hypothesis stated above are accepted.

Major Findings:

- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitude of teachers towards teaching profession. The mean teacher attitude score of female teachers in academic area was found to be greater than ($X=33.34$) their counter parts that is male Pre-service teachers ($X=31.20$).
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitude of teachers towards teaching profession. The mean teacher attitude score of female teacher in administrative area was found to be greater than ($X=19.50$) their counter parts i.e. male Pre-service teachers ($X=18.50$).
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitude of teachers towards teaching profession. The mean teacher attitude score of female teachers in co-curricular area was found to be greater than ($X=16.90$) their counter parts that is male Pre-service teachers ($X=15.80$).
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitude of teachers towards teaching profession. The mean teacher attitude score of female teachers in socio-psychological area was found to be greater than ($X=83.21$) their counter parts that is male Pre-service teachers ($X=81.10$).
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitude of teachers towards teaching profession. The mean teacher attitude score of female teachers was found to be greater than ($X=171.06$) their counter parts that is male Pre-service teachers ($X=164.20$) respectively.
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession in the area of academic aspect of attitudes male and female Pre-service teachers towards teaching profession.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession scores in the academic and co-curricular areas and total scores of rural and urban pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.

Conclusion:

There is a significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession scores in the areas administrative, academic, co-curricular, socio-psychological aspects and total scores of male and female Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level. There is no significant difference in the mean teacher attitude towards teaching profession scores in the administrative, co-curricular, socio-psychological, economic area and total scores of married and unmarried Pre-service teachers at B.Ed level.

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